

Powder diffraction pattern analysis and FT-IR spectrum analysis of tetrakis(4-aminopyridine-kN¹)-di chloride copper(II) monohydrate crystal

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Abstract:

This paper Investigates the Tetrakis(4-aminopyridine-kN¹)-dichloridocopper(II) monohydrate crystals prepared by the slow evaporation method and characterized by Fourier Transform of Infrared analysis and Powder X-Ray diffraction techniques. We observed strong absorption bands occur in FT-IR and confirm the functional group. The crystal crystallized in triclinic system and particle size, systematic absences all changes analysed by powder peak pattern of this crystals. The Size and Strain graph plot of Williamson-Hall plot and crystalline size distribution graph of Warren-Aver Bach method interprets strain coefficient, size coefficient and L graph of $(\Delta d/d)$ % versus length of peaks pattern predicted by PXRD data.

Keywords: Powder XRD, FT-IR, Williamson-Hall Plot, Warren-Aver Bach Method.

Reference

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